

Implantable Glucose BioFuel Cells for Medical Devices

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BioFuel Cells

Can we produce "power" for pacemakers (etc.) from fuel in the body

our cells use *electrolytes, ATP and other biochemicals* for "power"

cell membranes use proteins to transport electrolytes

can we build devices to produce "power" just like cells ?

"artificial cells" use proteins to transport electrolytes

Krishnamurthy V et al (2007). *IEEE Sensors Journal*. 7:1281-1288
 Battle AR et al (2009). *Advanced Functional Materials*. 19:201-208

The maintenance of optimum health requires more and more usage of implantable microsystems...

But providing the renewable energy to power these systems remains a challenge

Outline ...

- Energy scavenging to supply the power needs of the body
- Enzymatic bio-fuel cell
 - principles of the glucose bio-fuel cell,
 - physiological constraints,
 - implantation in an animal
- Biomimetic bio-fuel cell
 - mimic for physiological membrane transport
 - supported and tethered lipid bilayer membranes
 - producing power from biomimetic bio-fuel cell

Power for body function

How to provide a full range of power to drive artificial devices ?

Limits of sealed batteries

Cochlear implant:

Hidden external battery
350 μ W
Easy replacement

Outside the body

« Classic » pacemakers:

Lithium-Ion battery
15-40 μ W
Need replacement
7-10 years

Works well !

Artificial heart:

15-20W
Transcutaneous Energy Transfert
Time constraints
Possible damages

Not convenient
But Crucial...

Limits of sealed batteries

Cochlear implant:

Hidden external battery
350 μ W
Easy replacement :
outside the body

Power required >100 μ W

- rechargeable
- Improved power/weight ratio

« Classic » pacemakers:

Lithium-Ion battery
15-40 μ W
Need replacement
7-10 years

Power required < 10 μ W multiple places

- Rechargeable
- wireless

Artificial heart:

15-20W
TET technology
Time constraints
Possible damages

Pain management
Leadless pacemaker

How to scavenge power from the body?

➤ Physical power

Production limit = $100\mu\text{W}$ due to physiological constraints

(Kang J.Y. Encyclopedia of medical devices and instrumentation , 2006)

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Future leadless pacemaker ?

➤ Chemical power

What are the biofuels ...

- Always present in the body
- Producing electrochemical energy
- Produce non-toxic metabolites

Our Answer :

Glucose: 5mM

Dissolved oxygen: 40 μ M

Outline ...

- Types of implantable devices that could supply the power needs of the body
 - Sealed batteries ?
 - MEM devices ?
 - Scavenging energy from chemical substrates ?
- **Enzymatic bio-fuel cell**
 - principles of the glucose bio-fuel cell,
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Principle of a Glucose Biofuel Cell (GBFC)

Glucose oxidase fungus, insects

PPO, Laccase plants, fungus, insects

metabolism of glucose

lignin degradation

Oxidation of glucose, oxygen is reduced

Oxidation of (poly)phenolic compounds

GOX

Laccase

Every chemical reaction involves electrons.

Is it possible to « catch and release » these electrons?

Principle of a Glucose Biofuel Cell (GBFC)

Glucose oxidase fungus, insects

PPO, Laccase vegetal, fungus, insects

Oxidation of glucose :
release of H^+ and e^-

Reduction of oxygen :
capture of H^+ and e^-

The anode and cathode have, respectively, the roles of electron acceptor and donor instead of the "normal" substrates of these enzymes

Principle of a GBFC electrical wiring of the bioelectrodes

A. Zebda et al; Nature Commun.2011

The bioelectrode consists of a mechanical compression of enzyme & CNT
Miniaturization to operate in a rat

Physiological constraints

- Physical filter between the GBFC and the organism
- Biocompatibility
- Implantation site
- Wire connection

Physiological constraints

- Physical filter between the GBFC and the organism

A cellulose acetate membrane permits the free diffusion of glucose, oxygen and gluconic acid but blocks permeation of large molecules .

Physiological constraints

- Biocompatibility

Most of the actual implants are inert materials
Biofuel cells needs free diffusion of metabolites

Dacron® vascular prosthesis

The GBFC is wrapped in a Dacron mesh to promote tissue integration.

Physiological constraints

- Implantation site

Velho G, Diabetologica, 1989

Glucose diffusion in the ECF

The GBFC is implanted in the abdominal cavity of the rat.

The glucose concentration of the extra cellular fluid is equal to blood

Physiological constraints

Connector

- Wire connection

The connector is fixed on the skull

Tunneled catheter from the abdomen up to the head

GBFC

The technique is adapted to the rat ... avoid gnawing wires!

Health of the implanted animal

Exploring

Grooming

Playing

Normal weight of the animal
Normal food consumption

Normal behaviour

Power from an implanted GBFC ...

Practical application to power an electronic device

LED circuit design to test the electrical output of the GBFC

A high efficiency step-up converter was optimised to work with our GBFC and increase the voltage to at least 3V to flash a LED

The LED has flashed 5 times during 2minutes 30
Delivered a power output of 38.7 μW !

15 μW to 40 μW = Consumption of a pacemaker

Biocompatibility

Adipous tissue
richly vascularized

Active biomaterial:

Cells grow on the woven vascular prosthesis and neovascularization increases the exchanges

Coming back to the power output...

Cochlear implant:

Hidden external battery
350 μ W
Easy replacement :
outside the body

Power required >100 μ W

- Not rechargeable
- Improved power/weight ratio

« Classic » pacemakers:

Lithium-Ion battery
15-40 μ W
Need replacement
7-10 years

Power required < 1 μ W multiple localisations

- Not Rechargeable
- Problem of wires

Artificial heart:

15-20W
TET technology
Time constraints
Possible damages

Pain management
Leadless pacemaker

Coming back to the power output...

Delivered a power output of $38.7 \mu\text{W}$
from bioelectrodes of $240 \mu\text{l}$ volume

$161 \mu\text{W}/\text{ml}$ means ... $161 \mu\text{W}$ in a 1ml GBFC

... 1.61 mW in a 10ml GBFC
sufficient to supply the artificial urinary sphincter

... 16.1 mW in a 100ml GBFC
size of the first implantable pacemaker

... $1,61 \mu\text{W}$ in a $10 \mu\text{l}$ GBFC
leadless pacemaker power-supply

Outline ...

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Biomimetic Membrane Systems...

STIMULUS (sight, sound, touch, smell, temperature, toxin, pathogen, pharmaceutical, pesticide, heavy metal, micro-organism, ...)

natural - utilising proteins/lipids

change in biological function

utilising properties of man-made materials

physical/chemical/electrical output

nanobiotechnology

Biomimetic output

polyelectrolyte microcapsules

+
lipid coat

A = lipid-coated (dextran-FITC)
B = no lipid
C = lipid-coated (empty)

+
engineered ion channel

“switchable” ion channel activity

... “smart” capsules ...

Concept of biomimetic device ...

theory

Martin DK (ed.) "Nanobiotechnology of Lipid Membranes", Springer, NY, 2007

practical reality

Krishnamurthy V et al (2007). *IEEE Sens. J.*, 7:1281-1288
Battle AR et al (2009). *Adv. Func. Mater.* 19:201-208

implantable device

Cinquin P, Martin DK (2007). "Biomimetic artificial membrane device", PCT Nref 351528 D25694

Purification of membrane proteins in a cell-free system...

Pr JL Lenormand (TheREX, TIMC-IMAG), Synthelis SAS (UJF startup)

Yield per reaction
1-1.5 mg/ml

Liguori L et al. (2008). *Journal of Controlled Release* 126:217–227

Liguori L et al. (2008). *Curr Protoc Protein Sci.* Nov;Chapter 5:Unit 5.22

MeKaNo: generating power using nanobiotechnology

antiporter protein
electrogenically active
in biomimetic
membrane system

chambers are sealed
with biomimetic
membrane system

lipid bilayer + membrane proteins

~ 8 VDAC/100nm²
~ 10¹⁶ VDAC total

porous membrane support
+
polyelectrolyte membrane

Biomimetic and electrochemical power production

IBFC: Implanted BioFuel Cells

New electrodes

flexible polymers, porous silicon

Enzymatic Glucose BioFuel Cells

sugar \Rightarrow power

Biomimetic Fuel Cells

cell

protein

salt \Rightarrow power

Implanted BioFuel Cells

A common blockage: energy scavenging!

- Our objective is to make it possible for implanted robots designed to compensate for failure of physiological functions to scavenge their own energy from the body fluids
- Future works:
 - Improving the efficiency and longevity of the bioelectrodes
 - optimization of functional design of each component
 - biocompatibility
 - Implantation in bigger animals to test long term performance of the BioFue Cell

Ongoing development ... the team

Techniques for biomedical engineering and complexity management

The proof of concept...

The power to supply...

OPEN ACCESS Freely available online

PLOS one

A Glucose BioFuel Cell Implanted in Rats

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Single Glucose Biofuel Cells Implanted in Rats Power Electronic Devices

SUBJECT AREAS:
IMMOBILIZED ENZYMES
FUEL CELLS
BIONANOELECTRONICS
ELECTROCATALYSIS

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¹Univ Grenoble 1, CNRS, Département de Chimie Moléculaire, UMR 5250, ICMG FR 2607, BP 53, 38041 Grenoble Cedex 9, France, ²UJF-Grenoble 1/CNRS/TIMC-IMAG UMR 5525, Grenoble, F-38041, France, ³UroMems - 46 av. Félix Viallet - 38031 GRENOBLE cedex, France.

Ongoing development... ... the goals

ANR-10-NANO-03-02

**The aim of IBFC is to optimize the power output
of the enzymatic bio-fuel cell**

www.ibfc.fr

- Improving the efficiency and longevity of the bioelectrodes
- optimization of functional design of each component
- biocompatibility
- Implantation in bigger animals to test the biopile for the specific purpose (e.g. biosensors, stimulators)

... and also the biomimetic bio-fuel cell ...